

SCHOOL HEADS AND MASTER TEACHERS' COACHING SKILLS, PRACTICES AND TEACHERS' PERFORMANCE: IMPLICATION FOR EFFECTIVE INSTRUCTIONAL SUPERVISORY PLAN

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ABSTRACT

Even the well trained and knowledgeable teachers should possess a skill which reflects their leadership. School heads and Master Teachers may keep upgrading themselves so they can have much learning to share. Furthermore, School heads and master teachers may continue their post education to better improve their coaching skills. School heads and master may uphold coaching practices by continuously guiding teachers/coaches to find their own weaknesses and uphold their individual strength. The study aimed to determine the Coaching Skills and Practices of School Heads, Master Teachers, and Teacher's Performance. The quantitative study gathered 663 respondents from eight selected schools in Zamboanga City Division. Findings revealed that the school heads and master teachers highly manifested coaching skills in self-clarity; communication; critical thinking and ability to build relationship and inspire. This study showed that school heads and master teachers highly practiced coaching practices in coaching for improvement; coaching for maximum performance; coaching to strengthen skills, competencies and behavior. However, coaching skills have no direct correlation on coaches performance and do not vary in terms of years in service. In contrast, school heads and master teachers with doctoral units have better coaching skills than those school heads and master teachers who were doctoral holders who have lower skills compared to the other groups. This study made clear that there is a potential to develop a process where teachers could acquire skills they need through engagement to trainings, skill building and, practical teaching.

Keywords: School Head, Master Teacher, Coaching Skills, Leadership, supervisory plan